

Research Article

“G-D’s Physics”: The Universe’s New “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF) Center & “Geulah Driven Universe”!

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Note: *Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm based on a “time-sensitive” measurement of a predicted increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days’ time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish’s e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.*

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a basic “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New “G-D’s Physics” (“Computational Unified Field Theory”, CUFT) Scientific Paradigm! This “Paradigmatic-Shift” follows a fundamental “Paradigmatic-Crisis” signified by an apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between these two (GRT & QM) “pillars” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm and its principle inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion (e.g., assumed to comprise “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” comprising up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but which could not be verified experimentally even after two full decades of experimentation?!). In contrast, the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm was shown capable of resolving this apparent GRT-QM “theoretical inconsistency” and offering an alternative satisfactory explanation for the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion based on the discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at an incredible rate of “ c^2/h ” = 1.36^{50} (sec!) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) of the entire universe at “every minimal time-point”! In this study, two unique “Critical Predictions” of this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm have been empirically validated as “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, thereby substantiating it as the New Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! In addition, their empirical validation also points at the Centrality of a hypothesized “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF) as the functional center of the entire physical universe (e.g., in “time” and “space”), while negating the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s assumed “Big-Bang” Model and Darwin’s Natural Selection Principle’s Evolutionary Theory. Finally, the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm’s validation points at the beginning of the UCP’s “Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State” of the universe & Humanity, in which Science recognizes the singularity of this UCP as the basis for the physical universe, and in which Humanity lives in accordance with its “sublime” properties of “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

Introduction

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a major “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New “G-D’s Physics” (“Computational Unified Field Theory”, CUFT) [1-47]. This “Paradigmatic-Shift” inevitably followed the appearance of a fundamental “Paradigmatic-Crisis” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm signified by a basic “theoretical-inconsistency” between its (above-mentioned) constituting Models (e.g., GRT & QM), as well as its principle inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., assumed to be “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts, but could not be detected experimentally (despite over twenty years of intensive experimental efforts to do so)!! Instead, the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) has been shown capable of resolving this (apparent) “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM based on its discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features (e.g., of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and

“time”) of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – in the incredible rate of “ c^2/h ” = 1.36^{50} sec(!) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of UF’s frames comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”!

According to Thomas Kuhn’s⁵⁰ well-accepted analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions”⁵⁰, in order for Science to accept such a “Paradigmatic-Shift” (in any given scientific sub-discipline), it is necessary for a few specific conditions to be fulfilled:

a) The appearance of such a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” (in that given discipline) signified by the existence of a “theoretical-inconsistency” between the “pillars” of the Old (“Material-Causal”) Paradigm (e.g., GRT & QM, i.e., as mentioned above), as well as this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – e.g., assumed to “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all

the matter in the universe but which could not be detected experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so (despite twenty years of intensive experimentation)?!

b) The ability of the New ("G-D's Physics") Scientific paradigm to resolve this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM, as well as offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe: Based on "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's discovery of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle's" (UCP's) simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), it has been shown that this UCP simultaneously computes all "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) "particle/objects"; "Multiple Spatial-Temporal" (MST) "wave-phenomena"; and "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" "Universal Frame/s" computations! In this manner, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) as opposed to QM's "Quantum Entanglement" phenomena's implication wherein a certain measurement of one subatomic "entangled particle's" ("complimentary pairs" value may "instantaneously" affect the other "entangled particle's" complimentary (energy/mass or time/mass) value?! This is simply because according to "G-D's Physics broader EST computation – which embeds (within it) the relatively more "constrictive" UCP's MST and SST computations, the apparent "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon merely represents the UCP's computation of "equivalent SST particle points" along the MST's (subatomic) "wave" computation, which is embedded within the broader EST UCP's computation! Alongside "G-D's Physics" new (profound) theoretical understanding, wherein the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" is based on the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" i.e., "Framework" and "Consistency" four possible combinations: "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), and "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") possible combinations! Hence, "G-D's Physics" new theoretical framework has been shown capable of resolving this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's strict SLB's principle constraint imposed upon the transmission of any signal (or even information) across space and time – which seems to be contradicted by Quantum Entanglement's "instantaneous" effect of the measurement of one entangled particle's complimentary pairs' measurement upon the other entangled particle's complimentary value; based on the deeper theoretical understanding of "G-D's Physics" (novel) conceptualization and understanding wherein it is the simultaneous UCP's computation of "equivalent MST wave" "particle-points", coupled with its two "Computational Dimensions" complimentary exhaustive UCP's computation of "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time"), which can account for the apparent "entanglement" of two such "equivalent SST particle points" along the "MST wave" (simultaneous) computation of the UCP's "complimentary-exhaustive" "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") "complimentary pairs"!

Likewise, the New "G-D's Physics" theoretical framework offer a new (satisfactory) alternative theoretical explanation for the universe's empirically observed accelerated expansion! This new theoretical explanation of "G-D's Physics" is based on its (novel) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH) which stipulated that whenever there is a large group of individual human-beings all collectively focusing on this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), then this brings about an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE), e.g., such as during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" (New Year) two days' special time interval (in which Millions of Jews all over the world collectively focus on this singular UCP) – which was predicted to bring about such an "UNCIARE" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

c) Identification of at least one unique "Critical Prediction" which can differentiate the prediction of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM: according to Kuhn's [50] analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", in order for any scientific discipline to accept a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old ("Material-Causal") Paradigm to the New ("G-D's Physics") Paradigm it is necessary to identify at least one unique "Critical Prediction" that can differentiate the predictions of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm from the Old "Material-Causal" GRT's and QM's predictions! Indeed, if at least one such (unique) "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm is verified as "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions – then (according to Kuhn's [50] well accepted analysis) that particular scientific discipline (e.g., in our case Theoretical Physics) has to accept the New "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Physics Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century)! Indeed, we've been blessed with such an identification of two such (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which are being shown to be "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, therefore leading to the unequivocal acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)]= O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i..n) \leq n * h [UF's(i..n)]$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [54,56].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction Pohl et al.[54-56] set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily ac-

counted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force"[49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity [48], a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis π^+ [51], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion 58-61?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-ener-

gy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

A Brief Summary of "G-D's Physics" Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

a) The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

b) The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the

most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!? Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past" - "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral

Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed):

this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed"/חסד) Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah" may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/"גבורה"):

denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Tiferet"/"תפארת"):

the sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th , 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which

manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת"/Tiferet which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("Netzach"/"חצני"/"Eternal"):

signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "חצני"/"Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"/"חשובה"/"דוה"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State,

at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("סוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah term of "דוסי"/"Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "סוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"היכלות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent"

(mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yessod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "רתך"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")); This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ (sec⁻¹) for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

FIGURE 2. The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

The Centrality of “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF) in “G-D’s Physics” New Universe!

One of the key differences between the New (empirically validated) “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm and the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm is the “Centrality of Human Consciousness” – i.e., in “space” and “time”, and its intimate connection with the “Universal Consciousness Reality’s” (UCR’s) “Geulah Driven Universe” (GDU)! This is because according to “G-D’s Physics” New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm, it seems that “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF) plays a major role in the “Universe’s Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE)! As we’ve already seen, there is clear (and direct) empirical evidence for the centrality of this CHCF in terms of its UNCIARE’s acceleration in the universe! As outlined above, in contrast to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (e.g., which has been negated both based on the experimental failure to detect its existence experimentally, and “G-D’s Physics” principle computational negation of its associated Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s SRCS Computational Structure!) – which assumes that this (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept can only account for a “constant-rate” expansion rate of the universe; the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm points at an increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., “UNCIARE” due to the “Collective Human Consciousness Focus”, which occurs during the Jewish Rosh Hashanah’s (two days’ special) time-interval!

Indeed, it has been proven empirically (above) that it is solely based on this CHCF that the universe’s rate of expansion **increases over time**, e.g., as indicated by the (otherwise unexplained) “Universe’s Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UCAGUARE)!; An even more direct (further) validation of the centrality of the CHCF was called for Astronomers to validate during the upcoming two days’ Jewish Rosh Hashanah – during September 16th& 17th 2023, in which it is predicted that the universe’s rate of expansion will significantly increase (and continue to increase) during the whole ensuing Jewish year), relative to the universe’s measured rate of expansion in the preceding time prior to Sep. 16-17th! Moreover, previously it’s been shown that this same CHCF may be responsible for the Centrality of Human Consciousness – not just in “time” but also in “space”! This relates to the otherwise “unexplained” empirically validated phenomenon wherein the Astronomical measurement of the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion (UARE) also indicates that planet Earth stands at the center of this UARE! In other words, it may be the case wherein the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion – i.e., related to “space”, wherein it is only relative to planet Earth’s position that this accelerated rate of expansion pertaining to the furthest regions of space (wherein the farther any galactic element exists relative to planet Earth the faster its measured acceleration would be)! (for instance) it is found that such equivalent Astronomical measurements of the UARE – do not yield the same “symmetrical increase” in the universe’s UARE then this would validate the centrality of planet Earth (and its associated centrality of this CHCF) – in “space”, as well as in “time”!

“G-D’s Physics” Novel CHCF’s Center of the Universe Hypothesis!

We therefore reach an “astounding” new Hypothesis of “G-D’s Physics”, i.e., hypothesizing that at the center of the universe’s existence, dynamics and development – stand our planet Earth due to this CHCF, including the rotation of our sun (around it) and the accelerated expansion of other galactic elements “emanating” from planet Earth’s CHCF! This is because once we realize that the evolution of the physical universe cannot be explained merely due to an any initially assumed “Big-Bang” nuclear event- e.g., based on the empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm (above); and that (in fact), the basic SRCS Computational Structure of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm was shown to be negated by “G-D’s Physics” (novel) “Computational Duality Principle” (CDP) – i.e., as inevitably leading to both “log-

ical-inconsistency” and (ensuing) “computational indeterminacy” that are both negated by the CDP’s insistence upon the (proven) capacity of this apparently SRCS Computational System to determine the accelerated expansion of the universe – which (according to the CDP) points at the singularity of this singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF’s frame/s)! And most significantly, empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” (above) unique “Critical Prediction” regarding the “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE) – as more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’s assumed “constant rate” of the universe’s expansion rate! Therefore, we must negate (and reject) the Old “Material-Causal” GRT’s Paradigm’s assumption wherein the entire physical universe has been created (or “caused”) by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear even, and that its accelerated rate of expansion can be explained through the (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (which has been negated based on the three abovementioned considerations)!?

The alternative (novel) explanation offered by the New (empirically validated) “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- and development- of the whole physical universe is solely based on the operation of the singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that (solely) exists both “during” its computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s (as solely responsible for the computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel’s four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”!); And specifically, as associated with this UCP’s connection with the CHCF – which brings about the UCP’s initiation of the UNCIARE (empirically validated) phenomenon! In other words, the UNCIARE empirically validated phenomenon (unequivocally) proves that the origination of the entire physical universe, and its accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., as indicated by the “Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion”, CAGUARE) is brought about by the UCP’s consecutive computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s – and specifically by the CHCF’s UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., assumed to take place at every Annual “Jewish Rosh-Hashanah” two days’ time-interval (i.e., this year this will take place during Sep. 16-17th 2023 and onwards in which it is predicted the rate of the universe’s expansion will increase significantly, relative to the rate of the universe’s expansion prior to the 16-17th – which I’ve called Astronomers and Cosmologists to test experimentally!) Indeed, once we realize that the entire physical universe “dissolves” back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s and that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single- or multiple- UF’s frame/s; and therefore that the only “force” that creates- “dissolves”- re-creates- and evolves- any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is this singular higher-ordered UCP; hence, based on the clear empirical evidence indicating an UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion associated with the CHCF (hypothesized to take place during the Jew Rosh Hashanah!) we reach the inevitable theoretical conclusion wherein the expansion of the entire physical universe depends upon the CHCF – which brings about this UNCIARE increase in the universe’s expansion rate (beginning in each Jewish Rosh Hashanah and continuing throughout the entire subsequent Jewish Year).

We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion wherein taking together these two empirically validated facts:

a) Empirical Validation of “G-D’s Physics” UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, which according to G-D’s Physics is associated with the CHCF (e.g., specifically during the Jewish “Rosh-Hashanah” special two days’ time interval, as noted above: a call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test this UNCIARE-JRH during the upcoming Sep. 16th-17th, 2023 & onwards!) In other words, this UNCIARE (JRH) empir-

ically confirmed phenomenon points at the centrality of CHFC “in time”, i.e., specifically during the JRH (e.g., to be directly confirmed through the above call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test during the upcoming JRH!)

b) Centrality of Earth’s CHCF for the Universe’s Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! The empirically observed “unexplained” “Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion”) CAGUARE (indicates that the rate of the universe’s expansion has increased (significantly) from its early “Background Radiation” stage to the current (increased) rate in the universe’s expansion!)? This phenomenon is associated with Planet Earth’s “Epicenter” of the universe – in “space” (e.g., based on the fact that the accelerated rate of the our regions of the universe is proportional to the distance from “Earth”!)

Taken together, these empirically validated (major otherwise “unexplained”) phenomena point at the centrality of Earth’s “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” – in “space” and “time”: as the (functional) center of the universe! It also reinforces the singularity of the higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” as the sole source “originating” the entire physical universe (at the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec’)!)

Indeed, over and beyond the abovementioned empirical validations of “G-D’s Physics” two unique “Critical Predictions”, e.g., associated with the “UNCIARE” and “Proton-Radius Puzzle” findings, the two above empirical findings, i.e., regarding: a) Empirical Validation of “G-D’s Physics” UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, which according to G-D’s Physics is associated with the CHCF; b) Centrality of Earth’s CHCF for the Universe’s Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! clearly point at the Earth’s CHCF’s associated “Epicenter of the Universe” – i.e., both in “time” & “space”! Once again, if we wish to further validate in an even more direct manner the centrality of “Earth’s Epicenter of the Universe” (EEU) related to its CHCF (EEU-CHCF), then Astronomers are invited to test two additional unique “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm:

1) UNCIARE-JRH: as noted (above), an even more direct empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” New Scientific Paradigm, relates to a further testing of its additional “Critical Prediction” regarding the UNCIARE at the (upcoming) JRH (Sep. 16-17th 2023) in which it is predicted that the rate of the universe’s expansion will increase during these two days (and continue constantly throughout the next Jewish Year, relative to the rate of the universe’s expansion rate prior to Sep. 16-17th)!

2) EEU Validation: “Non-Earth’s Non-Epicenter Measurements” (NEN-EM)! An additional (even more direct) testing of the Centrality of Earth’s CHCF for the Universe’s Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion would be an empirical validation of a measurement of the universe’s “non-harmonious”, i.e., “non-equivalent” accelerated expansion rate – of the farthest regions of the universe, when measured at a location “distant” from Earth (e.g., such as for instance from “Mars” or other “distant” Non-Earth location)! This is because, if indeed, any such measurement of the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion (of a greater rate of expansion proportional to the distance from Earth’s measurement) would be found to be “un-equivalent” (in all directions – for all furthest regions of the universe), as opposed to the accelerated (“equivalent” or “harmonious”) rate of the universe’s expansion as measured from “Earth’s Universe’s Epi-center” (EEU), then this would indicate that indeed Earth’s (CHCF) Epicenter is in fact that the (functional) center of the entire physical universe!

In order to be able to accept this new (profound) metamorphosis of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which assume that the universe was created (or “caused”) by an initial “Big-Bang”

nuclear event (and is expanding due to a purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept which could not be verified experimentally and which is negated by the New empirically validated “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm, it is necessary to “retrace” the emergence of the basic “Paradigmatic-Crisis”, e.g., signifying this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm: indicated by the fundamental “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM, and its principle inability to explain the empirically observed accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion – assumed to be “caused” by the (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be verified experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so over the past two full decades?!). As we’ve seen, such a (fundamental) “Paradigmatic-Crisis” characterizes (according to Thomas Kuhn’s 1962 famous analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions”) the need for an ensuing “Paradigmatic-Shift” from this Old “Material-Causal” New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm! Indeed, the acceptance of the New “A-Causal Computation” “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm is dependent upon the fulfillment of few (stringent) criteria including: a) Capacity of the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm to resolve the (apparent) GRT-QM “theoretical inconsistency” (which has been shown previously stemming from the discovery of the singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features – at the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec’! thereby producing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”!) b) Offering an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion – based on the UNCIARE’s associated CHCF (outlined above); c) Identification- and empirical validation- of at least one unique “Critical Prediction/s” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’s & QM’s predictions! (Indeed, the abovementioned empirical validations of two such unique “Critical Predictions” related to UNCIARE and the “Proton Radius Puzzle” findings indicate that “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm is more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’ and QM’s corresponding predictions)!

Hence, based upon the fulfillment of these (stringent) necessary conditions for the acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) – points at “G-D’s Physics” as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century! It is important to note that this New “G-D’s Physics” was shown to resolve the apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM – and in fact unify between them based on its discovery of the (novel) “Universal Computational Formula”, which was also shown to unify (for the first time in Theoretical Physics) between the Four basic Physical Features (of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”), as well as between the Four Forces! Nevertheless, the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm was characterized as an “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, stemming from its discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF’s frame/s) and the complete “dissolution” of the entire physical universe “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frames (back into the singularity of the UCP)! According to this New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF’s frame/s! This profound new discovery made by the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm principally negates some of the most basic assumptions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, including: GRT’s “Big-Bang Model” and the existence of any purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept (as the assumed “caused” for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, as explained above).

Instead, “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm points at the fact that the whole origination-

sustenance- "dissolution"- and development of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety) has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP to evolve the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" in which Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which is also characterized by Humanity's (and Science's) "embracing" of this singular UCP's/UCR's intrinsic properties of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony"! Thus, the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm explains the whole origination- sustenance- ("dissolution"-) and development- of the entire physical universe: not as created by an initial "random" "Big-Bang" nuclear event, and the whole development of the universe – as leading to an ("inevitable") "dissipation" (e.g., based on the Second Law of Thermodynamics), which was shown to be negated by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm and its CDP; but rather as being "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR for the fulfillment of the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" (e.g., Morally, Spiritually and even Physically)! In that sense, the (above) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two (unique) "Critical Predictions"

"G-D's Physics" Unifies All Physical, Biological, Moral and Spiritual Facets of Human- & Universal- Development!

In this sense, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm completely unifies between the various facets, i.e., Physical, Biological, Moral and even Spiritual of the universe's and of Humanity! Once we realize that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g. existing either in the "same- or "different" UF's frame/s), and that therefore there cannot also exist any "material-causal" relationship/s or even "effects" existing across any two different (consecutive) UF's frame/s, we begin realizing that the only manner in which Theoretical Physics can explain (or describe) the "origination", "sustenance" or "development" of the universe (or of any "subsystem" found within it) – is solely based upon the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle"(UCP) or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which solely exists both "during" each consecutive UF's frame (e.g., as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features), as well as singularly exists "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., during which time the whole physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of this UCR)!? We realize that (based upon the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates) there truly exists only one singular higher-ordered UCR which manifests as the entirety of the physical universe "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but remains without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion that the existence of the entire physical universe merely represents a "transient" and "phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCR, e.g., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s but "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP/UCR! Hence, the continuous "origination", "dissolution" ("in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s of the entire universe back into the UCR), "development" and "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe is only geared at fulfilling this UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal" Objective which is to "steer" the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the realization of the singularity of this UCR by Humanity (and Science), which would lead to the "Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity (and the universe) in which Humanity lives in accordance with this singular UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony"! No longer, therefore, can we "hold on" to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption wherein both the origina-

tion of the universe by an assumed "random" "Big-Bang" nuclear event, as well as the origination of all Biological Species assumed to be "caused" by a "random" "material-causal" physical interactions between (certain) "genetically mutated – environmentally-compatible" specific organism/s and "challenging Environmental Conditions" (as opposed to other "un-mutated" organisms) which "caused" only those "genetically mutated – environmentally compatible" organism/s to "survive" and pass on their genetic information to subsequent generations?! This is because (once again), first of all there could not have been any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s either between the (initially assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event and the creation of any suns, galaxies, matter or energy etc. (e.g., in the "first", "second", "third"... "trillionth" etc. UF's frame – due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s); nor between those assumed "genetically mutated" organism/s and their "challenging Environmental Conditions" (e.g., at any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s) once again due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! Secondly, we realize that the whole development of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings must be "organized" and "directed" based on the UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's) which fulfill the UCP's/UCR's Ultimate Geulah-Goal Directed (GGD) Universe!

So, we obtain an entirely different conception of the whole origination-sustenance- "dissolution"- and development of the whole universe as "motivated" and "driven" by the singular higher-ordered UCR's "steering" of the universe towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! In that sense, the various facets of the universe's development – Physical, Biological, Moral and even Spiritual are all seen to be completely "integrated" as part and parcel of this "overarching", "preplanned" "Blueprint Plan" of the UCP to advance the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings ultimately leading to Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of this singular higher-ordered UCR and its associated "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony", constituting the fulfillment of the universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! Moreover, we (excitedly) realize that with the current article's acceptance of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm Science (and Humanity, more generally) are "entering" this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe, in which the singularity of this UCR is recognized and accepted by Science, and accordingly Humanity begins living in accordance with this singular higher-ordered "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

Dedication

This article is devoted to the Holy RASHBI (Rabbi Shimon Bar Yochai) on this Holy day (ל' ג' בעומר, תשפג) and to the 45 Holy fallen Jews on a previous day (ל' ג' בעומר) at Mt. Meiron. May the RASHBI's Eternal Inner-Torah Wisdom pointing at the singularity of G-D's existence, which was later on further revealed through the Baal-Shem Tov and all the Chabad Chassidic Leaders up until the current Lubavitcher Rabbi's Leadership to assist Humanity (and Science) enter this Ultimate "Geulah Perfected State of Humanity" (and Science)!

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